

Investigating Quality Trade-offs in Open Source Critical Embedded Systems (Supplementary Material)

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1. INTRODUCTION

In this document we make available supplementary material prevented from the data analysis performed within the case study presented in the paper entitled “Investigating Quality Trade-offs in Open Source Critical Embedded Systems”. The extra documentation comprises the **frequency table**, which summarizes the measurements obtained from all metrics; and

2. FREQUENCY TABLE

In this section we present the descriptive statistics (frequency table) from the analysis between quality attributes (QA), as described in **Step 1** of the data analysis procedure [1]. In Table 1, the rows of the table represent the scores that have improved, whereas the columns of the table represent the affected QA. Every group of four rows (delimited by bold lines) represents the analysis of one QA against all the others. For every set of columns (delimited by bold lines), we presented the following results, for both CES group (‘c’) and non-CES group (‘n’):

- the number of valid cases (in how many cases the considered QA has improved, in the corresponding group, represented by ‘#’);
- the percentage of cases in which the affected QA deteriorated (‘-’);
- the percentage of cases in which the affected QA improved (‘+’); and
- the percentage of cases in which the affected QA was stable (‘o’).

The percentages identified as valid evidence of trade-offs (see **Step 1.3** of the data analysis) are marked in bold. For example, considering *correctness* (improved) vs. *security* (affected), it is possible to see a valid evidence of trade-off in the group of non-CES, as the percentage of cases in which *security* deteriorated (46%) is higher than the other two (20% and 34%).

Table 1. Results of the interaction analysis between metrics

	Affected	correctness		security		performance		effectiveness		extendibility		flexibility		functionality		reusability		understandability	
		c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n
Improved																			
correctness	#			11	89	11	89	11	89	11	89	11	89	11	89	11	89	11	89
	-			36	46	55	39	36	51	73	48	27	49	45	33	45	35	55	57
	+			36	20	45	38	64	49	27	50	73	51	55	67	55	64	45	43
	o			28	34	0	23	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
security	#	10	60			10	60	10	60	10	60	10	60	10	60	10	60	10	60
	-	60	38			20	35	40	38	60	38	30	33	40	35	40	38	70	62
	+	40	30			60	37	60	62	40	53	70	67	60	65	60	62	30	38
	o	0	32			20	28	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
performance	#	11	93	11	93			11	93	11	93	11	93	11	93	11	93	11	93
	-	45.5	31	18	44			36	47	64	44	18	46	45	40	55	42	55	56
	+	45.5	37	55	24			64	53	36	46	82	54	55	60	45	58	45	44
	o	9	32	27	32			0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
effectiveness	#	25	241	25	241	25	241			25	241	25	241	25	241	25	241	25	241
	-	28	18	24	15	28	20			28	20	12	19	24	26	24	26	72	74
	+	52	35	40	37	48	41			60	67	88	81	76	72	76	71	28	26
	o	20	47	36	48	24	39			12	13	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
extendibility	#	15	199	15	199	15	199	15	199			15	199	15	199	15	199	15	199
	-	20	22	27	16	27	22	0	19			13	35	20	30	27	32	73	76
	+	67	36	47	41	53	44	100	81			87	64	80	70	73	68	27	24
	o	13	42	27	43	20	34	0	0			0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

	Affected	correctness		malicious_code		performance		effectiveness		extendibility		flexibility		functionality		reusability		understandability	
		c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n
Improved		c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n	c	n
flexibility	#	27	240	27	240	27	240	27	240	27	240			27	240	27	240	27	240
	-	30	19	26	17	33	21	19	19	41	33			22	26	26	28	67	71
	+	55	35	41	37	48	40	81	81	48	53			78	71	74	70	33	29
	o	15	46	33	47	19	40	0	0	11	14			0	3	0	3	0	0
functionality	#	25	283	25	283	25	283	25	283	25	283	25	283			25	283	25	283
	-	24	21	24	14	24	20	20	33	36	33	12	33			4	3	80	89
	+	56	34	40	37	48	40	76	61	48	49	84	60			96	97	20	11
	o	20	45	36	49	28	40	4	6	16	18	4	6			0	0	0	0
reusability	#	28	282	28	282	28	282	28	282	28	282	28	282	28	282			28	282
	-	22	20	21	13	18	19	29	33	46	34	25	34	14	3			79	90
	+	64	35	50	36	57	40	68	61	39	48	71	60	86	97			21	10
	o	14	45	29	51	25	41	4	6	14	18	4	6	0	0			0	0
understandability	#	20	192	20	192	20	192	20	192	20	192	20	192	20	192	20	192		
	-	25	20	15	12	25	21	65	66	75	66	55	62	75	81	70	82		
	+	55	33	35	39	45	38	35	32	20	24	45	36	25	16	30	15		
	o	20	47	50	49	30	41	0	2	5	10	0	2	0	3	0	3		

3. REFERENCES

[1] Feitosa, D., Ampatzoglou, A., Avgeriou, P. and E. Y. Nakagawa. 2015. Investigating Quality Trade-offs in Open Source Critical Embedded Systems. In *Proceedings of the 11th International ACM Sigsoft Conference on the Quality of Software Architectures* (Montreal, Quebec, Canada, May 2015). QoSA'15. 1–10. (submitted for publication)